

Predictions for Venus Cloud Discontinuities, Saturn Zonal Wind Slowdown, and 3I/Atlas Non-Gravitational Effects (2025–2037)

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Summary

There are some upcoming events I think will show manifestations caused by a hypothesized fifth force of nature. I list them here in chronological order.

- The interstellar object 3I/Atlas could experience extra non-gravitational acceleration during the period 1st September 2025 through 31st October 2025 due to its proximity to Mars.
- Cloud discontinuities will appear on Venus from 26th October 2025 until 26th March 2026 due to the influence of Mars.
- Saturn's equatorial zonal wind speed will significantly slow down from December 2025 until June 2037 due to the influence of Uranus.

These predictions are derived from a broader theoretical framework that explores a possible fifth force of nature. Details of the underlying theory are available at ltresearchblog.com. The rest of this post discusses supporting evidence for these claims.

Interstellar objects in the Solar System

For this extra force of nature to manifest, two objects must be unbound from each other. Therefore, the trajectories of the three interstellar objects, 1I/2017 U1 (Oumuamua), 2I/Borisov, and 3I/Atlas are of importance because of their unboundedness from the Sun.

1I/2017 U1

1I/2017 U1 would have manifested extra acceleration due to its proximity to Earth during the period 15th September 2017 through 10th November 2017. Additionally, it would have been affected by the extra field of Uranus from 12th September 2017 onwards.

Micheli et al. (Nature 2018) found a statistically significant ($\approx 30\sigma$) radial acceleration away from the Sun best fit by a $\Delta a \propto r^{-2}$ law.¹ The observational time span lasted from 19th October 2017 through early December 2017.

2I/Borisov

Analysis shows that 2I/Borisov would not have experienced extra forces due to any of the planets during its closest approach to the Sun.

Discovered on 29th August 2019, the object experienced normal non-gravitational acceleration due to cometary outgassing.

3I/Atlas

I expect 3I/Atlas to experience extra acceleration due to its proximity to Mars during the period 1st September 2025 through 31st October 2025 23:32 UT. Peak magnitude on 30th September 2025. Whether this magnitude is large enough to differentiate it from the effects of outgassing remains to be seen.

Conjunction of 3I/Atlas and Venus

The next object of interest is Venus. Incidentally, there will be a conjunction of 3I/Atlas and Venus on 31st October 2025. On this date, the extra force on 3I/Atlas caused by Mars will be significantly reduced due to the distance Mars-Venus becoming less than Mars-3I/Atlas. 3I/Atlas and Venus will achieve minimum separation of 0.688062° on 2025-10-31 20:09 UT (parabolic refinement of the 5-minute grid).

Figure 1: Conjunction of 3I/Atlas and Venus.

This brings us nicely to Mars' expected effect on the clouds of Venus.

Venus cloud discontinuity

Analysis shows many examples of cloud discontinuities coinciding with Venus being within range of Mars. It is hypothesized that Mars affects only the nearest spherical cap of Venus that contains

the same mass as Mars. This causes a standing wave, which in turn causes secondary waves that circle the planet every five days or so.

Figure 2 shows the regions of Venus affected during the period from 7th December 2015 through 11th December 2015. During this period, JAXA's Akatsuki spacecraft identified a prominent feature as shown in figure 3. Figure 4 shows the affected regions on Venus superimposed onto images taken by Akatsuki. Figure 5 compares cloud discontinuity observations with periods when Venus was in range of Mars. It's interesting to note that positive observations always occurred during these periods when the strength of $U(\text{Mars})$ was above 90% of the maximum value over the period 2015-26. The maximum strength over the period October 2025-March 2026 will be 95%.

Figure 2: Mars' effect on Venus. As viewed by JAXA's Akatsuki spacecraft. Arrow shows the direction of the hypothesized force. Straight red line shows the direction of Mars. Red line on planet shows the spherical cap base.

Figure 3: Venus cloud discontinuity in 2015.

Saturn's zonal wind slowdown

Figure 6 shows that Saturn has a strong prograde zonal wind profile. Also, figure 7 shows that $U(\text{Uranus})$ has been consistently positive for centuries. This means that \mathbf{U} has been pointing in the same direction as Saturn's equatorial winds. The exception to this was during the period 1979-1991 when $U(\text{Uranus})$ was negative. It was expected, then, that wind speeds during this period should have slowed down. Sánchez-Lavega et al (2003) indeed found a large decrease in Hubble's measurements of Saturn's equatorial jet during 1996-2002 compared to Voyager's measurements during 1980-81.² The next period where we should see similar values of $U(\text{Uranus})$ is December 2025 to June 2037. Figure 8 compares $U(\text{Uranus})$ for both periods.

Figure 4: Comparison between Mars' effect on Venus and Akatsuki's images.

References

- ¹ Micheli, M. *et al.* Non-gravitational acceleration in the trajectory of 1i/2017 u1 ('oumuamua). *Nature* **559**, 223–226 (2018).
- ² Sánchez-Lavega, A., Pérez-Hoyos, S., Rojas, J., Hueso, R. & French, R. A strong decrease in saturn's equatorial jet at cloud level. *Nature* **423**, 623–625 (2003).

Dates	Non-zero U(Mars)	U(Mars) max strength*	Cloud discontinuity		Publication
			observations		
2015-Oct-18- 2016-Feb-05	yes	32	yes		Nature Geosci 10, 85-88 (2017)
2016-Feb-06- 2016-Oct-03			yes		Peralta, J., et al Geophysical Research Letters, 47,11 (2020)
2016-Oct-04- 2017-Feb-11	yes	72	yes		J. Br. Astron. Assoc. 130, 4, 2020
2017-Feb-12- 2017-Aug-16					
2017-Aug-17- 2017-Dec-27	yes	56			
2017-Dec-28- 2019-Jun-17			yes		Peralta, J., et al Geophysical Research Letters, 47,11 (2020)
2019-Jun-18- 2019-Oct-27	yes	76			
2019-Oct-28- 2020-Jun-09			yes		Atmosphere 2022, 13, 348
2020-Jun-10- 2020-Jul-27	yes	81			
2020-Jul-28- 2021-Apr-16					
2021-Apr-17- 2021-Aug-27	yes	89			
2021-Aug-28- 2022-Feb-28					
2022-Mar-01- 2022-Jul-18	yes	100	yes		Peralta, J., et al A&A 672, L2 (2023)
2022-Jul-19- 2023-Mar-12					
2023-Mar-13- 2023-Jun-27	yes	97	yes		J. Br. Astron. Assoc. 135, 4, 2025
2023-Jun-28- 2023-Dec-27					
2023-Dec-28- 2024-May-29	yes	97	yes		Sedrani, R. Venus Image 2024/01/12. ALPO Japan.
2024-May-30- 2025-Oct-25			yes		Morrone, L. Venus Image 2024/07/17. ALPO Japan.
2025-Oct-26- 2026-Mar-26	yes	95	-		
2026-Mar-27- 2026-Oct-15					
2026-Oct-16- 2026-Dec-28	yes	93	-		

* percentage of maximum strength over entire period 2015-26

Figure 5: Cloud discontinuity 2015-26.

Figure 6: Saturn's zonal wind profile (adapted from Sánchez-Lavega et al, 2023). Green arrow represents the average long-term (1750-present) direction of $U(\text{Uranus})$.

Figure 7: Uranus effect on Saturn 1750-2200

Figure 8: Uranus' recent effect on Saturn.